

METHODS OF TEACHING LOGICAL CREATIVE THINKING TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In the given article the development of logical creative thinking in primary school, the effective organization of the educational process, students expressing their opinions and the formation of a personal worldview are discussed.*

Keywords: *primary education, logic, creative thinking, development, effective lesson, expression of opinion, personal worldview.*

It is known to everyone that a person's ability to manifest his potential, his personality, his abilities, his desire for freedom is a process that can occur at different periods of a person's life. The desire for progress, expanding one's worldview, and increasing the ability to express one's attitude towards events and developments is characteristic of every person. It is known that currently the main direction of personality-oriented education is the education and upbringing of children. Broad outlook, humanity, high moral and creative qualities are qualities that determine the level of human culture. As each person develops as an individual, situations arise that create creative qualities that believe in themselves and realize their potential.

Based on a creative approach to education and upbringing in order to implement personality-oriented education, each person is considered as a subject and the needs of his life are satisfied. Currently, attention to personal creativity and social demand is increasing. The development of students' logical thinking is one of the urgent tasks of secondary schools.

Using interesting tasks while organizing extracurricular activities in the lower grades is useful for subjects of the educational process, it gives the opportunity to independently think about a specific problem, analyze problems, feel responsible and independently work on solving them. form a personal point of view on a given problem, work in a group and team, plan and develop activities. In education, problematic situations are created for students through the organization of extracurricular activities.

It is true that a problematic situation is created through a training or practical situation and consists of two groups of components: known and unknown elements. A problematic situation is a state of intellectual tension in which a person feels a desire to get out of this situation and find a solution. A problematic situation requires a person to make a choice and a decision. This, he says, is "the beginning of critical thinking."

At present time, effective ways to develop creative thinking and creativity among young people have been analyzed. A particular attention is paid in our country to the education system; it is required that our students have modern knowledge and professional skills in accordance with world standards. Modern methods of developing such qualities as developing feelings of patriotism, humanity, and dedication to the profession are of great importance for them to grow up to be physically and mentally mature people, to reveal their abilities and talents.

In this regard, the President of our Republic also addressed the Oliy Majlis with the following appeal:

“For radical improvement the quality of education, first of all, it is necessary to bring educational programs, teaching aids for teachers and lecturers to advanced international criteria. To develop analytical and creative thinking in children, it is necessary to create meaningful and understandable textbooks for them. In this regard, in the next academic year, instead of the state educational standard in primary grades, the “National Curriculum” will be introduced, based on advanced foreign experience, which will not overload the children”.

It is important to discuss the concept of “creativity” which means “ability”. A person’s creative abilities are manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings and certain types of activities. Creativity characterizes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics, mental acuity. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent.

For improving the creative abilities of primary school students, various methods can be used in the classroom to make them think and develop their mental activity.

It should be suggested that in the process of learning to read and write, students are given different pictures and make a sentence out of them. For example, there can be shown cabbage, sun, apple and other pictures and ask students to try to draw a picture by looking at these pictures.

For example:

- Rabbits love to eat cabbage.
- In the morning the sun began to get hot.
- Students can make sentences like apples are ripe, red, which will enhance students' creative thinking.

Primary school textbooks contain different poems, riddles and proverbs. If the teacher is a creative person, they can be used in different ways. Through this approach, we can help students increase their creativity and think more creatively.

Critical thinking is a special type of thinking that draws conclusions by analyzing facts. The concept is complex and has various definitions, including rationality, skepticism, objective analysis, and fact-checking. Critical thinking is a form of thinking that is self-directed, self-disciplined, self-controlled and self-correcting. Its indispensable condition is agreement with strict standards for the improvement of consciousness and vigilant application of them. Critical thinking requires acquiring effective communication and problem-solving skills, as well as overcoming our inherent egocentrism and sociocentrism.

In conclusion, creative thinking sets a goal and ends with a desired outcome. The expected creative thinking skills are not characterized by the creation of unusual innovations, but by the fact that it is a creative activity that produces a desired result. Assessing students' thought processes helps identify effective and productive ideas. New ideas are discovered through these processes or existing ideas are modified. Processes of repetition and evaluation can be the basis of creative thinking. The skill developed by the ability to find flaws and comforts in the ideas brought by other people from the outside serves as the basis for working in a team.

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